

Voltammetric study and electrode kinetics of [Mn-sulfonamide-cephazolin] system at dropping mercury electrode

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Manuscript received 12 July 2007, revised 23 April 2008, accepted 6 May 2008

Abstract : Stability constants ($\log \beta$) of ternary complex of Mn^{II} with sulfadiazine, sulfisoxazole, sulfamethaxazole, sulfamethazine, sulfathiazole, sulfacetamide and sulfanilamide as primary ligands and cephazolin as secondary ligands were reported at $pH = 7.30 \pm 0.01$ at $\mu = 1.0 M NaClO_4$ at $25^\circ C$ by polarographic technique. The kinetic parameters like transfer coefficient (α), degree of irreversibility (λ), diffusion coefficient (D) and rate constant (k), were determined. The rate constants (k) that varied from $3.61 cm s^{-1}$ to $9.93 cm s^{-1}$ confirmed the quasi-reversible nature of electrode processes. The study was carried out at $25^\circ C$ and $35^\circ C$. Thermodynamic parameters such as entropy change (ΔS), enthalpy change (ΔH) and free energy change (ΔG) were determined. The values of stability constants ($\log \beta$) that varied from 1.75 to 9.13 showed these drugs or their complexes might be effective against Mn toxicity.

Keywords : Electrode kinetics, [Mn^{II}-sulfonamides-cephazolin] system.

Introduction

Sulpha drugs are a group of compounds used for eliminating a wide range of infections in human and other animal systems. Many chemotherapeutically important sulfadruugs like sulfadiazine, sulfathiazole, sulfamerazine, and sulfacetamide, possess SO_2NH moiety which is an important toxophoric function¹. Sulfonamides are drugs extensively used for the treatment of certain infections caused by gram-positive and gram-negative microorganisms, fungi, and certain protozoa². Metal complexes of sulfadruugs have been found to be more bacteriostatic than the drugs themselves^{3,4}. On the other hand, cephazolin is a member of cephalosporine drugs used in most of the infections and diseases therefore the metal complexes of sulfonamide and cephazolin with Mn have great importance.

Results and discussion

A well defined two electron quasi-reversible⁵ reduction wave of Mn^{II} was observed in $1.0 M NaClO_4$ at $pH 7.20$ to 8.50 at $25^\circ C$ ⁵, but $pH 7.30$ was selected to study the complex formation in the range of human blood pH ⁶. The nature of complexes was also quasi-reversible. Pure hydrogen gas was passed through the analyte for deaeration before recording the current-voltage curves.

[Mn^{II}-sulfonamide] system : The concentrations of

Mn^{II} , $NaClO_4$ and Triton X-100 were $0.5 mM$, $1.0 M$ and 0.001% respectively. The concentration of sulfonamide varied from $0.5 mM$ to $30.0 mM$ in each case. The half-wave potential $E_{1/2}^r$ became more negative with the addition of each sulfur drugs to Mn^{II} showing the complex formation. Gelling method⁷ was used to determine the $E_{1/2}^{reversible}$ values of metal and its complexes from $E_{1/2}^{quasi-reversible}$ values. The Deford and Hume method⁸ confirmed the formation of $1 : 1$, $1 : 2$, $1 : 3$, complexes of Mn^{II} with sulfadiazine, sulfisoxazole, sulfamethaxazole, sulfamethazine, sulfathiazole, sulfacetamide, sulfanilamide respectively. The values of stability constants of binary complexes were given in Table 1.

[Mn^{II}-sulfonamide-cephazolin] system : In this system the concentration of sulfonamide varied from $0.5 mM$ to $30.0 mM$ at $pH 7.30 \pm 0.01$ and $\mu 1.0 NaClO_4$ in the presence of 0.001% of Triton X-100 used as suppressor at $25^\circ C$. The half-wave potential values increased with the addition of cephazolin to the binary system i.e. [Mn^{II}-sulfonamide] showed ternary complex formation. Gelling⁷ method was used to determine the $E_{1/2}^{reversible}$ values from $E_{1/2}^{quasi-reversible}$ values of complexes. Schaap and McMaster method was used to determine the $1 : 1 : 1$, $1 : 2 : 1$, $1 : 1 : 2$ complexes. Plots of F_{ij} [X, Y] vs [X] for [Mn^{II}-sulfadiazine-cephazolin] system {where X and Y are sulfonamide and cephazolin and i and j are the

Table 1. Stability constant values of [Mn^{II}-sulfonamide-cephazolin] system
[Mn^{II}] = 0.5 mM, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄, pH = 7.30 ± 0.01, Temp. = 25 °C

Primary ligands	log β ₀₁	log β ₀₂	log β ₁₀	log β ₂₀	log β ₃₀	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁
Sulfadiazine	-	-	2.80	5.0	7.20	3.36	5.10	7.30
Sulfisoxazole	-	-	3.25	5.10	7.35	-	5.30	7.59
Sulfamethaxyzole	-	-	4.10	-	8.35	4.15	6.00	8.44
Sulfamethazine	-	-	4.15	7.20	8.40	4.28	7.33	8.55
Sulfathiazole	-	-	4.36	7.40	8.55	4.40	-	8.63
Sulfacetamide	-	-	4.51	7.61	8.75	4.48	7.65	8.63
Sulfanilamide	-	-	-	7.80	9.02	4.56	7.70	8.93
Cephazolin	1.58	2.48	-	-	-	-	-	-

stoichiometric numbers for primary and secondary ligands respectively} were given in Fig. 1. The probable structure of [Mn^{II}-sulfadiazine-cephazolin] system was given in Fig. 2. To determine the values of β₁₁ and β₁₂ the study was carried out at 0.025 M and 0.050 M of [cephazolin]. The stability constants were given in Table 1. The values of mixing constant (log k_m) which compares the stability of binary to the ternary complexes can

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Fig. 2. [Mn-sulfadiazine-cephazolin] system.

be given by the following equation⁹.

$$\log k_m = \log \beta_{11} - \frac{1}{2} [\log \beta_{02} + \log \beta_{20}]$$

The values of log k_m were -0.38, -0.20, -0.54, -0.565 and -0.58 for [Mn^{II}-sulfadiazine-cephazolin], [Mn^{II}-sulfamethazine-cephazolin], [Mn^{II}-sulfathiazole-cephazolin] and [Mn^{II}-sulfacetamide-cephazolin], [Mn^{II}-sulfanilamide-cephazolin] systems respectively. The negative values showed that binary complexes are more stable than their ternary complexes. In case of sulfisoxazole and sulfamethaxyzole, 1 : 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes were not formed therefore the values of log k_m were not reported for these systems. It is clear from the values of stability constants of complexes that sulfadiazine formed the complexes of minimum stability as its complexes showed the lowest values of E_{1/2} in comparison to the other sulfonamide complexes¹⁰. The stability constants of sulfisoxazole complexes are lesser than sulfamethaxyzole complexes is due to the presence of two -CH₃ groups in former than in the latter caused greater steric hindrance^{11,12} in sulfisoxazole complexes than sulfamethaxyzole complexes. Similar is the case with sulfamethazine and sulfathiazole com-

Fig. 1. Plot of F_{ij}[X, Y] vs [X] for [Mn^{II}-sulfadiazine-cephazolin] system.

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters of [Mn^{II}-sulfonamide-cephazolin] system at 25 °C and 35 °C

System	Stability constants				-ΔH (kcal/mol)				-ΔG (kcal/mol)				-ΔS (kcal/deg/mol)				
	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁		log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁		log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁		log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁		
	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	for difference of 10 °C (35 °C-25°C)	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C	25 °C/ 35 °C
[Mn-sulfadiazine- cephazolin]	3.36 2.98	5.1 4.68	7.3 6.82	7.3	15.9604	17.6404	20.1604		4.582 4.200	6.955 6.596	9.955 9.612		38.18261 38.18262	35.85795 35.85797	34.24715 34.24717		35.85795 34.24715
[Mn-sulfisoxazole- cephazolin]	- -	5.3 4.9	7.59 7.17	7.59	15.9604	17.6404	20.1604		- -	7.227 6.906	10.350 10.106		- -	32.12388 32.12390	24.46353 24.46355		32.12388 24.46355
[Mn-sulfamethaxyzole- cephazolin]	4.15 3.73	6 5.56	8.44 7.98	8.44	17.6404	18.4804	19.3204		5.659 5.257	8.182 7.836	11.509 11.247		40.20522 40.20523	34.55834 34.55836	26.21157 26.21159		34.55834 26.21157
[Mn-sulfamethazine- cephazolin]	4.28 3.93	7.33 6.95	8.55 8.15	8.55	14.7003	15.9604	16.004		5.837 5.539	9.996 9.796	11.659 11.487		29.74434 29.74436	20.01560 20.01562	17.25164 17.25167		20.01560 17.25167
[Mn-sulfathiazole- cephazolin]	4.4 4.02	- -	8.63 8.21	8.63	15.9604	-	17.6404		6.001 5.666	- -	11.768 11.586		33.42349 33.42350	- -	19.70441 19.70443		19.70441 19.70443
[Mn-sulfacetamide- cephazolin]	4.48 4.12	7.65 7.28	8.63 8.22	8.63	15.1203	15.5403	17.2204		6.109 5.807	10.432 10.261	11.768 11.586		30.23855 30.23857	17.14183 17.14185	18.29498 18.29501		17.14183 18.29498
[Mn-sulfanilamide- cephazolin]	4.56 4.12	7.70 7.24	8.93 8.43	8.93	18.8004	19.3204	21.0005		6.218 5.807	10.500 10.204	12.178 11.881		41.14788 41.14790	29.59786 29.59789	29.60700 29.60702		29.59786 29.60700

Note

plexes. In case of sulfacetamide and sulfanilamide, the former is the N¹-acetyl-substituted derivatives of sulfanilamide formed complexes with Mn having lesser stability constants than sulfanilamide complexes might be the fact that it has -CH₃CO group¹¹. The highest stability of sulfanilamide complexes amongst all other sulfonamide is due to the maximum shift of $E_{1/2}$ in its complexes¹⁰. The values of stability constants that varied from 1.58 to 8.93 confirmed that either sulfonamide or cephalosporin or its complexes could be effective against Mn toxicity¹³.

The kinetic parameters of [Mn^{II}-sulfonamide-cephalosporin] system were determined by Tamamushi and Tanaka methods^{14,15}. The values of transfer coefficient (α) varied from 0.42 to 0.54 (0.50) showed that the 'transition state' behaves between oxidant and reductant response to applied potential and it lies in the midpoint of dropping mercury electrode and solution interface¹⁶. The values of diffusion coefficient (D) and degree of irreversibility was as expected¹⁵. In case of cephalosporin, N of the β -lactam ring and O of the carboxylic group took part in bond formation with Mn thereby forming five membered ring¹⁷. The values of rate constant (k) varied from 4.05 to 9.42 cm s⁻¹ confirmed the quasi-reversible nature of electrode processes. A small variation in potential not only affects the rate but rate constant greatly.

The values of thermodynamic parameters so obtained were given in Table 2. The enthalpy contribution can be obtained experimentally by the temperature dependence of the stability constants¹⁸. The enthalpy changes of all complexation are found to be negative. The negative values of ΔH indicated the exothermic nature of the metal-ligand interaction¹⁹. The complexes were not stable at higher temperature which was confirmed by the values of ΔG and ΔS of complexes at higher temperature²⁰.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. Sodium salts of all the selected sulfur drugs and cephalosporin (Fluka, Sigma and Aldrich) were used. The pH of the analyte was measured on an Elico pH meter (LI-10) using glass and calomel electrodes and fixed at 7.30 ± 0.01 adjusted with dilute solutions of HClO₄ or NaOH as required. The polarograms were recorded on Polarographic Analyzer (Elico, Hyderabad, Model CL-362). The polarographic capillary was 5.0 cm long with diameter 0.04 mm with characteristics $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.04 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$. All the analytes were deaerated by pure hydrogen gas before recording the current-voltage graphs. Potassium dihydrogen phos-

phate-sodium hydroxide buffer was used to stabilize the pH of the analyte.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar, Madhya Pradesh for providing the laboratory facilities and M.P. Council of Science and Technology, Bhopal for enabling the Junior Research Fellowship to M. S. Parihar.

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